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Tier: Technology

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Executive Summary

This proposal describes a BioHackathon project to improve the usability and adoption of the ELIXIR Training Metrics Database (TMD), and is part of WP2 training platform work. The proposal focuses on lowering barriers to data contribution by introducing a user-friendly, form-based submission workflow alongside existing CSV uploads, and by refining the underlying data model to increase flexibility.

By making the TMD more accessible, this proposal aims to increase participation from ELIXIR nodes and improve the quality and coverage of training metrics, strengthening the ability to assess training impact and support decision-making.

The project aligns with the ELIXIR Training Platform (WP2) objectives and contributes to the long-term vision of a flexible, integrated, and widely used TMD, including future integration with TeSS and support for material-level metrics.

More information can be found in the TMD GitHub page <https://github.com/elixir-europe-training/Training-Metrics-Database> and the TMD wiki documentation here <https://github.com/elixir-europe-training/Training-Metrics-Database/wiki>.

Full proposal

Improving access and contribution workflows for the Training Metrics Database

Collaborations*

The TMD is a multi-node service, jointly administered by ELIXIR-SE, ELIXIR-FR, and ELIXIR-SI. In addition, other nodes are heavily involved in the development of the TMD, such as ELIXIR-GR. As the TMD is part of the ELIXIR ecosystem, we also collaborate with for example TeSS, where system integrations are a vital part. Lastly, the users of the TMD have a big role in the continued development of the TMD.

During the Biohackathon all these entities will come together to work on the proposed development. We will arrange user meetings with users to get their feedback on the suggested work, and meetings with the TeSS team to discuss further integrations and requirements.

All three co-leads of this proposal (Eleni, Olivier, and Nina) have previously attended the Biohackathon on-site as co-leads: [2024](#) (Nina, Eleni), [2025](#) (Nina, Eleni, Olivier).

Abstract

The Training Metrics Database (TMD) is an ELIXIR multi-node service that aggregates and assesses the quality and impact of training across the ELIXIR nodes. However, contributing data to the TMD can still be difficult for some users, limiting broader uptake and reducing the completeness of the collected metrics. This project aims to improve the usability of the TMD and lower the barriers to Node contributions.

During the Biohackathon, we will design and implement a user-friendly web-based submission interface to complement CSV uploads, including validation and clear guidance for users. In parallel, we will review and refine parts of the underlying data model, particularly the “Events” structure, to allow more flexible data entry without relying on hard-coded options. This will lay the foundation for further integrating the TMD and TeSS with regards to training material metrics.

Our project will assemble a cross-functional team of web developers and people involved in training and training impact, to ensure we deliver solutions tailored to the real user needs of the ELIXIR Training community.

The expected outcome is a more accessible, flexible, and practical TMD contribution workflow that will support wider adoption across ELIXIR Nodes and improve the quality and coverage of training metrics.

Scope and Vision

The goal of this project is to **lower the technical and usability barriers** that currently limit contributions to the ELIXIR Training Metrics Database (TMD), and thereby support broader adoption across ELIXIR Nodes.

During the BioHackathon, we will focus on two complementary objectives. First, we will improve the contribution workflow by designing and implementing a more user-friendly submission pathway, including form-based data entry to complement existing CSV uploads. This will make the system more accessible to contributors with different levels of technical expertise. Together with technical improvements the instructions and guidelines will be updated accordingly. Second, we will review and refine parts of the underlying data model, particularly the Events structure, so that data entry

becomes more flexible and less dependent on hard-coded values. Restructuring of the data model will also enable a future implementation of material metrics into the TMD, and the possibility of connecting material metrics with TeSS.

This project addresses a clear need within the ELIXIR Training community. Although the TMD is an important service for aggregating and analysing training impact across Nodes, not all Nodes currently contribute data, in part because interacting with the system can be difficult or inflexible. Lowering these barriers is essential for improving both the coverage and the quality of the collected metrics. This strengthens the ability to analyse training impact and supports decision-making at both node and ELIXIR levels.

With this work we will continue the work of integrating the TMD with TeSS, laying the foundations for material metrics support in the TMD.

This work is part of a longer development plan for the TMD, with the end goal of making it a fully flexible, user-friendly, and integrated system that is widely used in the ELIXIR community.

Alignment with ELIXIR 2024-28 Scientific Programme and beyond

This project aligns with the objectives under Work package 2 in the Training Platform programme, by enhancing the usability and interoperability of the TMD. The work programme focuses on adding functionalities to make the TMD more user friendly and support not only the ELIXIR nodes, but also communities outside of ELIXIR. This work also aligns with the proposed new WP in the 27-28 part of the work programme, with the goal of increased usability and node uptake, which will feed into the work to be done in the next part of the work programme.

This all feeds into the long-term goal, making the TMD a flexible, integrated, and externally usable service.

Feasibility

The long term goal of the TMD is regulated by the aims of the Training platform WP2.

The goal of the week is to achieve the following tasks, working in parallel working groups:

- Guiding users of the TMD through the submission process to identify weak points in UX design that can be improved
- Design of manual form submission work flow
- Database updates to Event tables to make it possible for users to update them
- Coordinate requirements with TeSS for future implementation of material metrics integration

Skills that are needed are:

- Python and Django API implementation
- Knowledge of TMD data and how nodes use it
- Design of user interfaces

As many of the participants are knowledgeable in Python and Django, many of them would have the competence needed for this project. We estimate a minimum group size of 5 to be able to do this project.

Inclusivity strategy

This project will be a hybrid project, with participants having the option to participate online during the week, making it accessible to everyone. The week will start with an introduction to the TMD for

newcomers to the project, and an update of the work that has been done previously. The TMD work lives on github, which will also be used during the hackathon, in an open repository.

This project is well suited for participants with diverse backgrounds, including developers, trainers, and Training coordinators. We will encourage participation from multiple ELIXIR nodes to ensure that different perspectives and training contexts are represented.

By dividing the work into technical and non-technical work, we hope to ensure that everyone can contribute with their knowledge without requiring technical expertise.

Link to proposal

<https://app.oxfordabstracts.com/stages/81806/submissions/1390468/form/view>

Outcomes and Impacts of the deliverable

This proposal is in line with the overall aim of expanding the TMD to make it more accessible and user friendly for all the Nodes, and other stakeholders interested in using the TMD. It supports the continued evolution of the TMD into a more accessible and integrated service for ELIXIR Nodes by expanding the user base and laying the foundation for further integration with TeSS.